

Fatigue assessment of two identical steel truss bridges

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ABSTRACT

It is not a simple task to assess the fatigue capacity of steel bridges in order to prolong their lifespan. The traffic load history for existing structures is rarely known in detail, constraints within the static system can often be difficult to estimate as well as the choice of the fatigue detail category. Too conservative assumptions may result in replacement of existing bridges, since minor overestimations of stresses have significant effects on the lifespan of the structure, due to the log-log relationship of the well-established S-N curves. One way of reducing uncertainties, related to loads and load-effects as well as to the dynamic effects, is to perform measurements on existing structures exposed to live loads. This paper presents the fatigue evaluation of derived fatigue stress-cycles based on rainflow counting (RFC) on measured data from two different, but identically built, steel bridges in Sweden. The Rautasjokk Bridge located along the Iron Ore line (Malmbanan) were found to be exposed to more and higher stress cycles compared to the Åby Bridge, located along the Main line (Stambanan). For the Rautasjokk Bridge, the trains loaded with iron ore were responsible for about 80% of the fatigue damage on the stringer beams. Presented in this paper is also a comparison of theoretical methods for fatigue assessment, prescribed in the Swedish bridge assessment code. Furthermore, suggestions for improvement of theoretical assessment methods are also presented.

Keywords: Bridge structures, Fatigue, Structural Health monitoring, Stress cycles

1 INTRODUCTION

The Åby Bridge (*Figure 1- Mid*) and the Rautasjokk Bridge (*Figure 1 - Right*) are two 33 m long, 4.9 m high and 5.5 m wide unballasted open steel truss rail bridges of Warren type with verticals, located in Northern Sweden (*Figure 1- Left*). The bridges were built using the same set of drawings. The rail is supported by wooden sleepers, which rest directly upon longitudinal stringers. The stringers span 4.125 m between cross beams. The complete set of bridge drawings are included in (1).

Figure 1. Left: Location of the two bridges, Mid: bridge over Åby river Right: bridge over Rautasjokk.

The superstructures were designed for train load F46, corresponding to 12 axles with 25 tonnes axle loads at 1.6 m spacing, representing the locomotive, and a distributed load of 85 kN/m representing the wagons (2).

The Åby Bridge was built in 1957 and was located along the Swedish “Main line” until 2012 when it was replaced by a ballasted steel trough bridge. The Rautasjokk Bridge was built in 1962 and is still in service. The major difference between the bridges is that the Rautasjokk Bridge is located along the “Iron Ore line” and therefore subjected to heavier loads, due to mining activities in the area. The allowed axle load on the Iron Ore line where 30 tonnes at the time the data in this report were collected but has since then been increased to 32,5 tonnes, while it was 25 tonnes for the Åby River bridge on the Main Line.

The bridges over Åby River and Rautasjokk have together been tested in three phases:

- Åby Bridge – Strain, displacement and acceleration measurements under live loading
- Åby Bridge – Strain and displacement measurements while statically being loaded to failure
- Rautasjokk Bridge – Strain measurements under live loading

The measurement programs and the results from these measurements are presented in (1) and the static test to failure is described in (3). A local approach for fatigue assessment, using hot-spots (4) is presented in (5) for the Rautasjokk Bridge. Here local strains measured on the flanges of the stringer beams were compared to nominal strains extrapolated from measurements on the web. Considering the fatigue lifespan, the hot-spot method was found favourable in one out of three studied locations. This might, however, be explained by out-of-plane action, which is evaluated in (6).

A capacity assessment (7) according to the Swedish bridge assessment standards (8) was carried out for the Rautasjokk Bridge. The report identified the gusset plate, welded to the top flange of the stringers for horizontal bracing, as a critical detail with regard to fatigue. Despite this, no cracks have been found during inspections, For the Söderström Bridge in Stockholm, the same type of detail was identified as critical, also without observed cracks (9).

Data presented in this paper was retrieved from the live measurements of strains from the Åby and Rautasjokk bridges. Strain gauges were attached to the bridges by welding, and data were sampled using HBM-hardware together with Catman Professional software.

For the Åby Bridge there are 389 registered trains, which were sampled over a period of 14 days. For the Rautasjokk Bridge there are 526 registered trains, which were sampled over a period of 25 days. The data was sampled at 50Hz for the Åby Bridge and at 400Hz for the Rautasjokk bridge. Both frequencies are considered to be sufficient for counting the stress-cycles.

In this paper, measurements are used for Strain gauges located at the Quarter-point of the Bottom chord (SQB), seen in *Figure 2*, as well as from Strain gauges located on the First Stringer (SFS), seen in *Figure 3*. In *Figure 3*, there are five sections presented (SFS 1-5) with four sensors each, in this paper only SFS3 is investigated and for simplicity referred to as SFS. The instrumentation is thoroughly described in (1 & 6).

Figure 2. SQB-sensors Upper: position of the sensors symmetrically positioned on each side of the main truss. Lower: SQB1_1, SQB2_1, SQB2_1, SQB2_2

Figure 3. SFS-sensors on the first stringer beam close to the support

2 METHOD

The WAFO-toolbox (10) for Matlab was used to identify local peak-values and to run the Rainflow algorithm (11) to extract load cycles. Load-cycles are filtered so that only stress-cycles that give rise to fatigue damage is considered leading to the detail category having an impact on the number of identified stress-cycles.

For the evaluation of stringers beams, a mean value is used of the two sensors on the top flange (SFS3_1 & SFS3_4) and the two sensors on the bottom flange (SFS3_2 & SFS3_3). The same operation is used for the SQB-sensors with the mean value for the SFS1&2_2 sensors.

The detail category of the stringers was set to $C = 50$ MPa. The detail comes from the gusset plate, welded to the top flange for the horizontal bracing, identified as critical for fatigue (7).

The main truss has a similar detail, which gives rise to the same detail category. Based on the monitored strains only a handful stress-cycles gave rise to any fatigue damage – therefore the detail category was set to $C = 36$ MPa for the purpose of being able to compare the two bridges.

3 RESULTS

Strain-cycles from the RFC (Rain Flow Counting) were extracted for the whole reference period of the measurements for both Åby and Rautasjøkk bridge.

From Figure 4 it can be seen that the number of load cycles for stringers are significantly higher than for the main truss. It can also be noted that the Rautasjøkk Bridge is subjected to more and higher loads than the Åby Bridge.

By transferring strains to stresses using Hookes law, the measured load cycles can be used for fatigue evaluation. In Figure 5 the stress-cycles are presented with the number of trains normalized to 10^6 train sets. The figure is made in log scale together with the Wöhler curve creating an S-N diagram. Out of 526 registered trains passing the Rautasjøkk Bridge, 130 were identified as trains transporting iron ore going in the northern direction. The contribution from these trains is highlighted in Figure 5.

Figure 4. Strain cycles: Left: SQB-sensors, Mid: SFS-sensors (top flange), Right: SFS-sensors (bottom flange)

Figure 5. Stress-histogram for the measured response normalized to 10^6 train passages based on RFC together with the Wöhler curve for C36/50, C71 and C90. Upper left: SQB. Upper right: SFS top flange. Lower: SFS bottom flange.

The results from Figure 5 are presented in Table 1, “Max-Min” is the fatigue damage when one stress-cycle is considered per passing train, the ratio RFC/Max-Min corresponds to the number of stress-cycles that should be considered in fatigue assessment per passing train, Mean damage per trainset⁻¹ is the number of trainsets that theoretically can pass the bridge before depleting its fatigue capacity. For both bridges roughly 2/3 of the trains give rise to fatigue-damage in the position of SQB-sensors with the number of damaging load cycles per train being close to 1 even though the growth of fatigue-damage is about 3.5 times higher per train for the Rautasjokk Bridge.

For the stringers the difference between the two bridges is greater. For the Åby bridge, about 1/3 of the trains gave rise to fatigue damage and for the Rautasjokk Bridge about 2/3. The Rautasjokk Bridge is subjected to about 3 times as many load cycles per passing train where the average fatigue damage for the Rautasjokk Bridge is about 30 times higher than the Åby Bridge, much due to the repeated heavy loading of Iron Ore trains. For the results presented in Fig.5 and Table 1 the accumulated damage was found to be 1.75-2.75 times higher when overestimating the stress-width by 20%.

Table 1. Summation of damage

		No of Trains	No. of Trains damage > 0	No. of damaging stress-cycles	Sum RFC Damage (10 ⁻³)	Sum Max-Min Damage (10 ³)	Ratio RFC/Max-Min	Mean damage per trainset ⁻¹ (10 ⁶)
SQB-sensor Main truss	Åby	389	279	290	0.02179	0.02122	1.027	17.849
	Rautas	526	356	376	0.10442	0.10405	1.004	5.0371
SFS-sensor top flange Stringer	Åby	389	137	1149	0.033911	0.0057004	5.9488	11.471
	Rautas	526	360	12608	1.5628	0.070515	22.163	0.33657
SFS-sensor bottom flange Stringer	Åby	389	161	1410	0.050944	0.0074866	6.8047	7.6358
	Rautas	526	457	13277	2.0508	0.098113	20.902	0.25649

4 FATIGUE ASSESSMENT

According to the Swedish bridge assessment code (8) existing railway bridges are to be verified for their fatigue capacity using either “typified stress-collective”, accounting for the accumulated damage based on the hypothesis of Palmgren-Miner or measurements. The general procedure is to start with more simple calculations using a “typified stress-collective” and if the requirements are not fulfilled to account for accumulated damage based on load history for the given line. The use of measurements for fatigue evaluation is only used in special cases.

4.1 Typified stress-collective

This method is a direct approach for fatigue assessment, taking a mix of traffic into account while still using constant amplitude stresses by the use of the collective parameter (κ), which considers the variation of load-cycles related to the maximum load in a logarithmic way.

A Collective-parameter of 1.0 is equivalent to all stress-cycles being of the same magnitude as the maximum.

The background for typified stress collective is described in (12) and explained in in (13). The collective parameter can be illustrated as in *Figure 6* where κ represent the slope of the line for a logarithmic cumulative horizontal histogram. If the collective parameter is lower than 1.0 the procedure is to increase the characteristic fatigue class, in accordance with table 6:524 in (14).

Figure 6. Illustration of collective parameter with typified load cycles

The collective parameter for the Main line (Stambanan) is $\kappa = 2/3$ and for the Ore line (Malmbanan) it is set to $\kappa = 5/6$ (8). The number of cycles, that needs to be considered for the analysis, is 10^6 cycles if the influence length of the detail is longer than 6 m (12 m for Malmbanan); otherwise, the detail should be controlled for 10^7 cycles. The reason for Malmbanan having a higher collective parameter is mainly due to the uniformed heavy traffic from iron ore trains. Studying *Table 1* supports the reason for assessing shorter influence lines for a higher number of cycles as well as the reason for the higher collective parameter on Malmbanan.

In an attempt to determine the collective parameter from the measured response, the RFC-cycles were considered. From the measured strain-cycles the 10 highest stress-cycles were removed. The remaining ones were normalized to the biggest stress-cycle and binned to a total number of 30 bins with the highest being 1.0. Based on the results, the accumulated response plotted and a curve-fit through $y = 1.0$ added as seen in *Figure 7*. For the analysis, cycles below the limit for fatigue-damage are not taken into consideration. The collective parameter is thereby dependent on the detail category, by definition the collective parameter is also highly dependent on the highest stress-cycle. The estimated collective-parameter is not linear as illustrated in *Figure 6* even if the slope of the trend line is in line with standards (0,674 to be compared with $2/3$ and 0,776 to be compared to $5/6$).

Figure 7. Estimated collective parameter based on the SFS-sensors for the top flange.
 Left: Åby bridge ($\kappa = 0,674$). Right: Rautasjokk ($\kappa = 0,776$)

4.2 Accumulated Damage

The load history of an element or bridge must be known in order to assess the accumulated damage with the Palmgren-Miner hypothesis. Based on the load history, the number of trains is derived and for a given train type the maximum stress variation ($\Delta\sigma$) is calculated and the load cycles per train are determined by either the number of axles, bogies or trains.

The measured strain for a train passage of the Åby Bridge is presented in Figure 8. The train consisted of two locomotives and 36 wagons each with 4 axles. It can be seen that the main truss is subjected to one major load cycle, the crossbeam to one major as well as to 38 minor ones and the stringer to 36 full cycles and 36 half cycles from the wagons as well as 4 cycles from the locomotives.

There is no doubt about the main truss only receiving one load cycle, however it can be debated on how to assess the crossbeam and stringer in a direct approach based on the maximum strain/stress width. The semi-cycles presented for the crossbeam and the stringer only has an impact if the cycle is big enough to give rise to fatigue damage. If disregarding gigacycles this means that stress-cycles lower than 40,5% of the nominal detail category does not have any influence. It can thereby be concluded that the number of cycles which has to be considered are not only given by the influence length of the studied detail, but also on the load level and the fatigue sensitivity of the component. In some cases, empty wagons will give rise to unloading and thereby more cycles.

Figure 8. Strain variations for passage of a uniformed loaded train over the Åby bridge. The top green curve is the one cycle for the main truss, the middle red curve with many medium cycles is for the stringer and the bottom blue curve with many small cycles is for the cross beam.

In *Figure 9* the mean strain is presented for the SFS-sensors on the bottom flange of the stringer during the passage of an iron ore train. The circles indicate local max/min-points. By running the RFC-algorithm a total of 73 load cycles were detected. The RFC-damage for this specific passage is however only 43 times as high as the damage for only considering one load cycle, despite the uniformed loading and the stringers being completely unloaded between each cycle. It is not always an intuitive process to determine the number of load-cycles.

Figure 9. Strain variations in the SFS sensor for passage of an Iron-ore train on the Rautasjokk bridge. The max strain rate of ca 200 $\mu\epsilon$ corresponds to a stress range of ca 42 MPa

4.3 Measurements

In the case where measurements are used for fatigue assessment, critical details with regard to fatigue are to be monitored for the period of at least one week (8).

It is often claimed that strain gauges do not lie, which in most cases is true. However, the measured strain is not necessarily what the engineer requires. For the analysis it is generally the nominal strain that is used, meaning that stress-concentrations due to geometric discontinuities are taken in to consideration by the fatigue-class and not the stress-level. This makes evaluation by using measurements less straightforward. There are different methods for dealing with this problem, for example; the measurements can be carried out some distance away from the critical detail or the sensors can be mounted on the web and extrapolated to the flange given that the critical detail is on the flange.

A different approach is to use the hot-spot stress instead of the nominal stress. By using the hot-spot-method the geometric stress-raising effect is included in the stress-level rather than the fatigue-class. The idea with this method is to measure the strain in a few points (2 or 3) and thereby extrapolate the so called hot-spot-stress to the weld toe (4). For field studies this method can prove difficult, since the sensor-positioning is very precise, and a minor mis-location of only a few mm of the strain-gauges can provide completely different results. Some measurements and results of hot-spot-measurements on the Rautasjokk Bridge are presented in (5).

When using measurements for assessing bridges (8), the load-history is to be considered by proportionating the tonnage during the measurement-period with that of the load-history. This approach can only be considered as valid if the axle-loads and geometry have been constant over the

lifespan of the bridge. For bridges like the Rautasjokk bridge, where the axle loads have increased almost with a factor of 2 since taken in to service, this statement is over conservative. From the results presented in this report, it can be stated that a reduction of loads by 30% can enhance lifespan about 5 times or more.

5 PROCEDURES TO PROLONG FATIGUE LIFE

In the cases where a specific detail has been found theoretically inadequate due to fatigue it is not necessarily a need for major concerns. Bridges can often continue to be in operation but with shorter intervals between inspections.

One action which that can be taken in order to improve the fatigue-capacity is to improve the specific detail. For steel structures, fatigue cracks are often initiated from welds, specifically from sharp corners. By grinding, it is sometimes possible to improve and smoothen the corners and by doing this, increase the detail category. An example of this type of weld treatment was done on Söderströmsbron (15).

During 2020 this type of procedure was also done on the Rautasjokk bridge, and by doing so improving the detail category to C71. The method of improving this specific detail is now implemented in Swedish procurement reference document (16). Methods to prolong life exemplified on the Åby bridge are also given in (17).

Figure 10. Methodology of how to improve fatigue life through grinding away materials inside the half circle in the figure.

6 CONCLUSIONS

To make an accurate assessment of a steel-structure with regard to fatigue often proves to be difficult. This is due to the non-uniformed load and the logarithmic relationship between stress-width and load-cycles. By using over-conservative assumptions, the lifespan of a specific detail is often reduced multiple times and can rule out a structure having capacity to be operational for several more years. Based on the results presented in this paper it can be concluded that the Rautasjokk Bridge is exposed to more fatigue damaging traffic compared to Åby Bridge. For the main truss, the Rautasjokk Bridge is in average exposed to 4.1 times the damage compared to the Åby Bridge per passing train. Considering the stringers, the difference is about 30 times higher for the Rautasjokk Bridge. The significant difference between the two bridges is mainly due to the Iron ore trains along the route. The loaded trains going North from Kiruna to Narvik were found to be responsible for 85-90% of the accumulated damage on the stringers. These trains are heavily loaded with an unfavourable axle configuration with regard to the stringers.

If the period of measurements (14 days for the Åby bridge and 25 days for the Rautasjokk Bridge) are assumed representative as normal traffic for the two bridges, the accumulated damage would be depleted after 33 years for the bottom flange (of the stringers) for the Rautasjokk bridge while the Åby bridge would last 750 years.

The collective parameters were not found to be linear, especially not for the Rautasjokk bridge.

7 DISCUSSION

It was not possible to recreate the typified collective parameter in a linear satisfying way, however the use of the parameter can still prove useful. Instead on trying to fit a linear curve, the collective parameter should be calibrated for the actual fatigue damage based on measurements of real axle loads or measured strains.

The authors believe that using constant stress-width for assessment of existing structures is not a good approach for accurate results. It might serve as a conservative initial estimation, but if these results prove unfavourable more detailed analysis should be performed.

In this paper the growth of fatigue-damage has been estimated based on S-N curves and Palmgren-Miner's hypothesis of accumulated damage from strain-measurements using RFC. The authors believe that this type of approach reduces many of the uncertainties related to conventional methods. Measurements provide accurate results provided that the measurements are done correctly. Performing long-term strain-measurements are however not always feasible, but the same technique can be used for a simulated analysis. By defining an influence diagram for a specific detail and knowing the axle-configuration and axle weight (which is possible to extract from measurement stations) it is possible to simulate response for the detail, and thereby using the same technique.

In order to reduce calculation time, load history can be binned but still taking variations of axle loads within the train-set into considerations by for example using stochastic variables. This procedure might appear time-consuming, but can fairly easy be embedded into a software, where a more accurate load-history than what is normally being used today, could be used. An example of a software, which uses this approach, is BridgeFat (STRECO Engineering Solutions AB).

8 REFERENCES

1. **Häggström J., Blanksvärd T.** (2017) Bridge over Åby River - Evaluation of full scale testing. Luleå, Technical report, Division of Construction and Structural Engineering, Luleå University of Technology, Luleå, Sweden 180 s.
2. **Trafikverket** (2010) Tåglaster genom tiderna. (Train loads through the ages, in Swedish), version 3.3, Sweden.
3. **Häggström J., Blanksvärd T., Collin P. and Tu. Y** (2017) Full scale testing to failure of a steel truss railway bridge. ICE (Institution of Civil Engineers), Bridge engineering, 12pp.
4. **IIW (International Institute of Welding)**. Recommendations for fatigue design of welded joints and components. Paris, France, October 2008
5. **Häggström J., Blanksvärd T. and Collin P.** (2016) Fatigue assessment of stringer beams using structural health monitoring. 19th Congress of IABSE (International Association of Bridge and Structural Engineering), Stockholm, September 21-23, 2016.
6. **Häggström J** (2016) Evaluation of the Load Carrying Capacity of a Steel Truss Railway Bridge: Testing, Theory and Evaluation. Licentiate Thesis, Luleå University of Technology, 2016. 139 p.
7. **Häggström J.** (2014) Bärighetsberäkning: Bro över södra Rautasjokk Km 1432+883. Luleå. (Load-carrying capacity for the bridge over South Rautasjokk at km 1432+883. In Swedish), Technical report, Division of Structural Engineering, Luleå University of Technology, Luleå, Sweden 352 s.
8. **Trafikverket** (2016) Bärighetsberäkning av broar (load carrying capacity for bridges) TDOK 2013:0267 Version 3.0. Trafikverket.
9. **Leander J** (2008) Bron över Söderström, Rapport 1: Mätning och utvärdering m.a.p. utmattning (Bridge over Söderström, Report 1: Measurements and evaluation with regard to fatigue)
10. **Brodtkorb P.A., Johannesson P., Lindgren G., Rychlik I., Rydén J. and Sjö E.** (2000). "WAFO - a Matlab toolbox for analysis of random waves and loads", Proc. 10th Int. Offshore and Polar Eng. Conf., Seattle, USA, Vol III, pp. 343-350. <http://www.maths.lth.se/matstat/wafo>.
11. **Rychlik I.** (1987) A New Definition of the Rainflow Cycle Counting Method, Int. J. Fatigue 9:2, 119-121.
12. **Alpsten G.** (1974) Utmattningsdimensionering enligt nya Byggsvetsnormen- experimentell bakgrund och beräkningsfilosofi. (Fatigue Design according to new welding code – Experimental background and methods of calculations. In 'Swedish). Väg- och vattenbyggaren 11, 1974
13. **SSAB** (2010) Plåthandboken – Att konstruera och tillverka i höghållfast stål. (Steel Handbook – To Design and Construct in High Strength Steel. In Swedish). SSAB Svenskt stål AB (publisher) Borlänge : SSAB Center of Excellence, cop. 2010, 250 s. ISBN 9789197857314
14. **Boverket** (2007) Boverkets handbok om stålkonstruktioner (BSK07) Boverket, Version 4, ISBN: 978-91-85751-58-7, Dnr: 1226-3574/2007, Elanders Sverige AB
15. **Andersson A., Leander J and Karoumi R.**, "Extending the fatigue service life of a railway bridge by local approaches, IABSE Conference, Rotterdam May 6 - 8, 2013 Assessment, Upgrading and Refurbishment of Infrastructures, 2013. 16.
16. **Svensk Byggtjänst** (2023) Allmän Material och Arbetsbeskrivning (AMA) GBD.3
17. **Elfgren, L., Bell, B., Nilimaa, J., Häggström, J., Tu, Y., Lundgren, K., ... Casas, J. R.** (2015). New technologies to extend the life of elderly rail infrastructure: Deliverable 1.3 in MAINLINE - EC 7th FP, 194p. <https://www.diva-portal.org/smash/get/diva2:998078/FULLTEXT01.pdf>